

Press Release

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Kick-off of CRYPTOACTION: A Horizon Europe Project to Combat Cryptocurrency-Facilitated Crime and Terrorism

Athens, Greece, 24- 25 September 2025

On 24-25 September 2025, the **CRYPTOACTION consortium** officially launched its Horizon Europe project with a **two-day kick-off meeting** hosted in Athens. The event brought together experts, researchers, and law enforcement representatives from across Europe to set the foundation for a collaborative effort in tackling cryptocurrency-facilitated crime and terrorism (CFCT).

CRYPTOACTION represents Europe's ambitious initiative in equipping Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) with **cutting-edge, interoperable, and trustworthy AI-enhanced tools** to support investigations into illicit cryptocurrency activities. Over the course of **42 months**, the project will deliver a **holistic ecosystem** of lawful investigation tools, advanced training curricula, and the world's first **cryptorange** - a dedicated environment for LEAs to train and test anti-CFCT technologies.

The **project's mission** is to confront major challenges that hinder investigations, including darknet marketplaces, TOR, mixers, decentralized exchanges, and privacy coins. At the same time, it will foster **secure information sharing and collaboration among European and international stakeholders**. By embracing the **EU's seven principles of trustworthy AI**, CRYPTOACTION will provide transparent and explainable tools, while also contributing to **future regulatory and policy recommendations**.

During the kick-off, consortium partners agreed on the project objectives, governance, and dissemination strategies. Sessions focused on the design and validation of investigation tools, the structure of the cryptorange training environment, strategies for LEA engagement, and cross-border capacity building workshops. Discussions further addressed ethical and regulatory considerations, data protection issues, and the importance of interoperability with existing systems. The meeting emphasised the central role of co-design with Law Enforcement Agencies to ensure real-world impact and operational usability. Above all, it highlighted the strong commitment of all consortium members to **foster innovation, strengthen investigative capacity, and enhance Europe's resilience** against emerging cyber-enabled threats.

Coordinated by **European Dynamics Luxembourg SA**, the consortium brings together 16 partners and 2 associated organisations from 8 countries, including research institutes, technology providers, ministries, and law enforcement agencies.

The launch of CRYPTOACTION marks **an important milestone** in Europe's collective fight against cryptocurrency-facilitated crime. By combining AI-driven innovation with strong cross-border collaboration, the project will provide law enforcement with the tools they need to stay ahead of emerging threats and will pave the way towards a safer and more secure digital future.

The CRYPTOACTION team:

EUROPEAN DYNAMICS LUXEMBOURG SA (Luxemburg)

EUROPEAN DYNAMICS ADVANCED INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND TELECOMMUNICATION SYSTEMS SA (Greece)

SCORECHAIN SA (Luxemburg)

HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE ENGINEERING EPE (Greece)

IANUS TECHNOLOGIES LTD (Cyprus)

Functori (France)

AEGIS IT RESEARCH GMBH (Germany)

ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS (Greece)

EREVNITIKO PANEPISTIMIAKO INSTITOUTO SYSTIMATON EPIKOINONION KAI YPOLOGISTON (Greece)

KENTRO MELETON ASFALEIAS (Greece)

MINISTERE DE L'INTERIEUR (France)

CIVIPOL (France)

SISAMINISTERIO (SM) (Finland)

YPOURGEIO ETHNIKIS OIKONOMIAS KAI OIKONOMIKON (Greece)

Cyprus police (Cyprus)

INSPECTORATUL GENERAL AL POLITIEI (Moldova)

21 Analytics AG (Switzerland)

UNIVERSITAT ZURICH (Switzerland)

Stay tuned with the CRYPTOACTION project by following the project's LinkedIn page. The official project website will be launched soon.

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